

MEDICAL SCIENCES

LIFESTYLE OF MEDICAL STUDENTS OF OSH STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The article presents the modern lifestyle of students of the International Medical Faculty of Osh State University and the characteristics of medical and social factors affecting the health of students. Students of medical universities, in comparison with other universities, they always have a busy time, there is not always enough time for timely meals and sufficient sleep. However, the results of these processes come to a more serious violation. It is right to allocate time for rest, without compromising academic (and in the future – working) time to start with student life. Acquiring the skills of proper management of temporary resources allows you to increase personal efficiency, teaches you to highlight the most important things at the moment. According to survey done the conclusion is more than 50% of college students are not able to have meal at time due to strict college schedule. Very serious issue among college students is that they are not able to perform extra curricular activities due to lack of time which would have helped in knowing skills in different activities. This article contains suggestions to improve mental and physical health. The article review will concentrate on the prevention of stress and method of doing good with yourself being a student, to improve sleep and wake cycle and balanced diet.

Aims: To determine the lifestyle and occupational health hazards in the life of medical students, with the further development of recommendations to improve the quality of life.

Keywords: Students mental health, Sleep deprivation, skipping meals, screen time, depression, extra-curricular activities, college schedule.

In the modern world, people are more absorbed in work, study, important things and often experience not just fatigue, but a feeling of emotional burnout. A stressful situation, fear, untimely meals affect students to adapt to a new lifestyle, and in the worst case, acquire bad habits. The beginning of a new student life at medical universities will greatly affect the lives of students, due to the fact that the educational material they receive is very difficult to understand on their own, without the help of a teacher, which is the cause of more stress. Many students who consciously approached medical universities were able to spend time for themselves, and some students fell into panic, despondency, self-pity, fear-mongering, which, of course, negatively affected their health and emotional state.

Materials and Methods of research. Study and analysis of literature, questionnaire, method of comparative analysis, comparative analysis of the results obtained, generalization.

The ongoing situation in learning institutions is worth raising eyebrows, and therefore it deserves serious attention. Many factors and conditions are almost same for students. As we follow modernization we have to also keep an eye on mental health of students, they should be physically, emotionally and socially strong. In the context of getting higher grades and a tougher competition, we have forgot to talk about an average individual who have to compete and compromise even with sleep and eating habits. Most of the

learning institutions have very tight schedules and continuous sequences of study, which affects the students performance and their mental well-being.

Health is the first and most important need of a person, determining his ability to work and ensuring the harmonious development of personality. Unfortunately, many people do not observe the simplest, science-based norms of a healthy lifestyle. Some become victims of inactivity (inactivity), which causes premature aging. Others abuse food, provoking the development of obesity, vascular sclerosis, metabolic disorders. Still others do not know how to relax, distract themselves from mental and everyday worries, always restless, nervous, suffer from insomnia, which ultimately leads to a variety of psychosomatic diseases. Some people, succumbing to the addiction to smoking and alcohol, actively shorten their lives. According to the research results, the reason for the presence of bad habits in students is stress caused by the overload of curricula, the lack of normal relaxation mechanisms. As we know the basics of a healthy lifestyle include: work and rest regime, sleep organization, nutrition regime, organization of motor activity, prevention of bad habits; psychophysical regulation of the body.

In our work, we would like to reflect the most important components of a healthy lifestyle of a student, which will be presented below. Understanding the importance of a well-organized study regime, rest, sleep

regime, diet, we conducted a survey among students of the International Medical Faculty.

The raising hot topics of concern for medical students is to know how they manage their busy college schedule with proper sleep. The first question is how do

you cope with the study schedule with proper sleep, 47.9% are trying to cope, but 25% say that they can't cope because of a busy lesson, and 21% of students say that they are correcting with studies and there is no sleep mode.

(1) How you manage your schedule of college with proper sleep ?

211 responses

By not maintaining proper schedule students are torturing themselves and affecting health, as they cannot take proper rest and also unable to complete work on time. Set goals, prioritise tasks, make note of deadline, make note of deadlines, start with small work and make it your habit, do things by pre planning, in the night decide what you will do in the next morning, take small breaks and in those breaks also do some relaxing work, take help from others, reward yourself when you have completed your daily to do task.

Sleep is a mandatory and most complete form of daily rest. For a student, it is necessary to consider 7.5 - 8 hours as the usual norm of night monophasic sleep. Hours intended for sleep cannot be considered as a kind of time reserve that can be used often and with impunity for other purposes. This, as a rule, affects the productivity of mental work and the psycho-emotional state. The results of the survey of students showed us that about 26% of students observe the sleep regime, 44% sleep -6 hours, and even worse there are students who sleep only -5 hours (14.2%) and 4 hours (15.6%).

(2) How many hours a day you sleep ?

211 responses

Sleep deprivation could lead to serious health disorders like-risk of hypertension, diabetes, obesity, heart attack, decreased brain function, memory loss, weakened immune system, psychiatric disorders. Despite the importance of your studies, but it is no more than your mental work. You should always try to take care of your sleep, its effectiveness will increase your efficiency, and you will feel more energetic and rested. At least 6 hours of restful and uninterrupted sleep at night and completing college work in the afternoon - early morning classes are more valuable than late evening classes.

should know the principles of rational nutrition, regulate their diet. Food serves as a source of energy for the work of all body systems, tissue renewal. Part of the energy goes to the basic exchange necessary to maintain life in a state of complete rest, about 30 - 40% of the energy goes to ensure physical and professional activity of a person. During their studies, students make up their own diet, educational institutions also take into account the time on nutrition when drawing up the lesson schedule. But our surveys show that more than 50% of students skip meals during their studies, about 22% only observe the diet, and there are still students who sometimes observe but also sometimes skip.

Nutrition plays a significant role in the formation of a healthy lifestyle of students. Every student can and

(5) How often you skip meals because of college schedule ?

211 responses

If meals are not taken or in proper balance it can lead to weight loss, feeling tired, weaken energy, skin and hair problems, lower metabolism, menstrual irregularity. Obviously for this problem there are many solutions, students should be given with healthy and little amount of breakfast that will help to maintain balanced diet and reduce eating time. In their lunch some fruits, salads, juices can be packed with them in addition to food so they can eat by sharing, this will increase their diet and they will learn social interaction. Dinner time should be 3 hours prior to sleep so that the food get digested easily and help sleep better. An important aspect of the food culture is the regime and the distribution of calories of food during the day. The maximum amount

should be given breakfast, 40-50% of the calorie content of the daily diet should fall on the morning meal, about 25% remains for lunch and dinner.

One of the mandatory factors of a healthy lifestyle of students is the systematic use of physical activity. They are a combination of various motor actions performed in everyday life, in organized and independent physical exercises and sports. A large number of people engaged in intellectual work have limited motor activity. This is also true of students, 56% of whom say that they do not have time for sports. But there are students who actively lead a healthy lifestyle, doing sports (34.1%), and even more interesting were students who prefer sports more than studying.

(6) How much time you spend in sports and other activities than studies ?

211 responses

“A healthy mind stays in a healthy body” is not just a statement, not a fact to focus on, students should be good both in school and in extracurricular activities. Students justify themselves not getting enough time for hobbies due to college schedules. The general perspective should be that sports should be encouraged in educational institutions and extracurricular sports events should be organized, there are many different competitions among students.

To lead an active lifestyle, one of the key is considered to be proper time management, specific compilation and time management. The above questions show that many students do not observe sleep patterns, do not exercise. And we were interested in their success

in the classroom and spending time preparing university homework, spending time on social networks.

Our attention is drawn to the fact that young people who view the weather while studying or for other social applications spend a lot of time in front of the screens of mobile devices or laptops. The life of a modern person can no longer be imagined without such things as a tablet, phone, computer. Uncontrolled use of gadgets by a child also does not lead to good, so gadgets should be in the life of students, but dosed. Most of our students spend 6-8 hours on the study screening, not taking into account other social networks. Various achievements of science in the form of technological gadgets — all kinds of laptops, computers,

smartphones, the Internet and TV have become so firmly embedded in our lives that it is now difficult to even imagine it without them. We all understand that in a world that depends so much on communication technologies, fast search and exchange of information, technical skills are simply necessary for everyone. But

if you abuse gadgets, the negative consequences will not keep you waiting. The most common is visual impairment, impaired posture and physical inactivity, memory impairment and the ability to concentrate if the child is sitting at the computer for a long time and in the wrong position.

(3) What is your screening time, for study or for entertainment purpose a day ?

208 responses

(4) How you feel due to screen time you suffer from ?

210 responses

The main rule is to maintain a balance in everything. No virtual game can replace real activities: creative activities, sports, outdoor games, reading books, walking.

It is necessary to monitor each student's screening time, on average it is 30-50 minutes a day. If the lesson requires more time, then take breaks for 10 minutes and do not miss gymnastics for the eyes. Try not to use gadgets before going to bed: such activity before falling asleep excites the nervous system, the child may not sleep well, have difficulty falling asleep or have nightmares. No worries screen time can be reduced by playing outdoor games rather than mobile games, by study-

ing from books and reliable sources, use of eye protective glasses can also reduce eye stress. And talking to friends more directly rather than chatting or calling will be helpful.

The following diagram shows that students spend a maximum of 4 hours a day (45%) on self-preparation, and this means that the rest of the screening hours are for other social networks. Having spent more time in gadgets and having difficulties in communication, they often become dependent on social networks and chat rooms. In such cases, not only communication with peers suffers, but also relationships in the family, universities.

(7) How much time you spend on self study per day ?

211 responses

(9) What are the reasons of not studying properly ?

208 responses

A very strange situation is that currently students do not practice meditation or physical exercises to maintain health, but spend more time on social networks. And the reasons for unsuccessful studies, the majority of students answered as a lack of time for preparation (51.5%), and the other 29.3% simply forgets the topics they have passed, 15% do not take into account due to health. After all, physical exercises and meditation, listening to soothing music can help them become more beautiful and turn their innovative ideas into reality.

After entering medical life students feel emotional burst leaving home for studies first time for a while is

not easy. Students feel study depression, tension of cracking competitive exam and despite of the fact that they need to talk about their mental health to parents, sometime they cannot share these things because they think parents might get stressed with all that, they don't want to panic parents. According to a report by the TrustedSource Board of Medical Education, stress, burnout and depression are risk factors for medical students with serious consequences. The Council reports that medical students are three times more likely to commit suicide than the general population. The survey results we conducted also show that the majority of 30.5% of students felt depressed during their first year.

(8) What you feel at which year you started feeling depression ?

200 responses

If the student talks to their parents, supervisors, they will help them make the right decisions, because parents and teachers are more mature emotionally, mentally and socially stable. And for sure they will show them the right way of life, it would be easy to get access to the mental state of the students.

But an interesting fact we have turned out that the causes of their depression are often due to stress 31%, insufficient nutrition (29.3%) and sleep 25%, and of course indicated due to more loss of time for screening.

(10) If you feel headache or depression, what is the reason ?

208 responses

“Medical students report higher levels of psychological distress than their same-age peers, despite having similar or healthier profiles than peers at the outset of medical school,” according to a 2018 study Trusted Source. The results of various studies show various stress factors for medical students, such as: academic stress, problems with work-life balance, conflicts in relationships, poor guidance or support of students, amount of information, finances, uncertainty about the future, lack of time for yourself, responsibility, the need to be successful.

A 2018 study surveyed 1,137 medical students in Florida and found that “stress levels increase during medical school, peaking either in their sophomore year or when students enroll in medical departments.”

Sources of stress in medical school may vary depending on your year of study:

- Academic workload was the biggest stress for first-year students, while financial difficulties were the lowest stressor.

- For second-year students, competition with peers was the most stressful.

- Third-year students had the highest work-life balance conflicts, romantic relationships, family demands and personal medical conditions.

- As for the fourth-year medical students, the most intense stress was coming into contact with human suffering.

Solution: Fix your schedule to sleep at 9 Pm. 6 hours sleep is enough, if you oversleep, or sleep less then you might get some mental disorders like depression. Have poor memory. Eat 3 hours before bed it help in asleep faster, get rid of heartburn, and enhance health. Perform a simple workout to eliminate brain fog. Plan your morning a night before, find a way to create flow in your morning hours. Look at your schedule, align your priorities, schedule tasks to handle first. Take a glass of water, drinking water on empty stomach will help you: lift your mood, reduce food cravings, eliminate the sluggish feeling. Eliminate screen time 1

hour before bed. This will help fall sleep in 2-5 minutes. Get rid of phone addiction and quit overthinking in bed.

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